

Thermal-Hydraulic and Reactivity Analysis of a Passive Molten salt Fast Reactor (PMFR) Under Marine Rolling Motion

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ABSTRACT

The global urgency to decarbonize energy production, including the marine sector, has driven increased interest in alternative, eco-friendly power sources for shipping, particularly nuclear-powered ships. The Molten Salt Reactor (MSR), a Generation IV concept, is highly applicable to marine environments due to its inherent safety, compact design, and high thermal power density. However, the unique characteristics of its liquid fuel and the external forces (wind, waves) inherent to the marine environment necessitate a thorough evaluation of the resulting thermal-hydraulic and reactivity changes under ship motion. This study investigates the behavior of a Passive Molten salt Fast Reactor (PMFR) under rolling motion by employing a one-way coupled analysis using the OpenFOAM and the Serpent code. Rolling motions with maximum angles of 5°, 30°, and 40° (with a fixed 10-second period) were analyzed. The thermal-hydraulic analysis revealed that the core mean temperature and its maximum-to-minimum difference increased with the rotation angle, showing a fluctuating trend corresponding to the rotational period. For the 40° case, the mean temperature rose by approximately 3.4 K, and a substantial local temperature difference of up to 100 K was observed. Consistent with this, the neutronics analysis showed that the effective multiplication factor k_{eff} oscillated inversely to the mean temperature trend. Notably, the observed change in k_{eff} was larger than expected based on the mean temperature difference, which is attributed to non-uniform, localized temperature variations across the core. The results emphasize that this rotational motion causes distinct, shifting high- and low-temperature regions, which is expected to significantly complicate the power density profile during actual transient states.

Keywords: Molten Salt Reactor, Multi-physics, Marine motion, OpenFOAM

1. INTRODUCTION

Climate change poses a significant threat to both humanity and the natural world. To limit the average global temperature, increase to 1.5 °C, global energy production needs to be decarbonized by around 2050. This transition requires a near-complete shift to low-carbon energy sources within the next 30 years, moving away from a system largely dependent on fossil fuels. CO₂ emissions from the marine sector account for approximately 2% of the global energy-related CO₂ emissions, with 87% of this being generated by the shipping industry, including bulk carriers, oil tankers, and container vessels [1]. Environmental regulations enacted by the International Maritime Organization (IMO) have been rigorously enforced to reduce pollution from ships. These stringent regulations have prompted the shipbuilding industry to seek alternative eco-friendly energy solutions, leading to a growing interest in nuclear-powered ship [2].

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Molten salt reactor (MSR), which is one of Gen IV reactor is regarded as having high applicability to the marine environment due to its advantages, including high inherent safety, compact design, and high thermal power density [3]. The main feature of MSR is utilizing liquid fuel, typically consisting of fluoride- or chloride- based carrier salts containing soluble fissile materials. The high boiling temperature of molten salt can remove the boiling crisis from the reactor system, and high melting temperature is evaluated to reduce the hazard of fission product release by solidification of liquid fuel during the accident.

While the liquid fuel of the Molten Salt Reactor offers numerous advantages, the unique characteristics of the marine environment necessitate consideration of other factors. Due to the nature of liquid fuel, the temperature distribution can change rapidly in response to flow variations. The high thermal feedback of the MSR may induce transient states corresponding to these temperature fluctuations. Specifically, in a marine environment where external forces such as wind and waves can generate external motion, it is essential to evaluate the resulting thermal-hydraulic behavior and reactivity changes of the reactor. Therefore, this study performs an evaluation of this phenomenon by coupling the OpenFOAM thermal-hydraulic analysis with the Serpent code.

2. TARGET REACTOR AND NUMERICAL METHODS

2.1. Reactor Design Concept

The Passive Molten salt Fast Reactor is one of molten salt reactor, which aims long-term operation of over 20 years and high safety without severe accident by operating under natural circulation condition [4-7]. To achieve these goals, the PMFR consists of a tall primary system approximately 10 m in height, and many components near the active core region to enhance neutron economy. Figure 1 shows the conceptual design of PMFR. A cylindrical active core with a height of 1.95 m and a radius of 1 m, is located in the lower part of the reactor, and the heat generated from the active core rises through the riser. The working fluid that flows upward, is cooled in a helical heat exchanger surrounding the riser, then descends through the downcomer to be re-injected into the core, thus forming a natural circulation. For long-term operation, the core contains only liquid fuel, and reactivity is controlled by a control drum that surrounds the core. The detailed design parameters of reactor are presented in Table I.

Figure 1. The conceptual primary system of passive molten salt fast reactor

Table I. Numerical condition for OpenFOAM transient analysis.

Parameter	Description
General plant data	
Reactor thermal output	200~300 MWt
Fuel type	Molten salt-Uranium eutectic
Plant design life	> 40
Primary coolant material	NaCl-KCl-UCl ₃
Reactor height	10~15 m
Primary circulation type	Natural circulation
Heat exchanger type	Helical Coil
Reactor Core	
Active core height	1.95 m
Active core diameter	2 m
Fuel material	NaCl-KCl-UCl ₃
Burnable absorber	B4C (installed in control drum)

2.2. OpenFOAM calculation

OpenFOAM is free C++ library for the solution of various numerical problem. In this study, buoyantPimpleFOAM was selected to solve the thermal-hydraulic behavior of PMFR because the buoyantPimpleFoam is transient solver for buoyant and turbulent flow. Figure 2 illustrates the core geometry and mesh utilized in this analysis. To reduce computational load, the analysis was performed solely on the core region, which comprised a total of 3,563,934 meshes. The core is partitioned into the inlet region, where the fuel salt injects from the down-comer, a flow guide structure designed for internal flow homogenization, and the outlet leading to the riser region. For simplification, it was assumed that fission occurs only within the active core region, and the power distribution was adopted from the profile calculated by Serpent. The flow rate entering the core was assumed to be a uniform value, leveraging the results from a previous natural circulation analysis [8]. Detailed numerical conditions are summarized in Table II.

It should be noted that the objective of the OpenFOAM analysis is not to simulate the overall reactor thermal-hydraulic behavior under ship motion, but to isolate and investigate the direct influence of externally imposed body force variation on the local thermal-fluid fields inside the active core region under a prescribed flow condition. Therefore, the inlet mass flow rate is intentionally treated as a fixed boundary condition based on the previous natural circulation analysis, and potential system-level effects such as degradation of natural circulation are outside the scope of the present study.

Figure 2. Geometry and mesh of active core region of PMFR

To account for marine motion, the tabulatedAccelerationSource under the OpenFOAM fvOptions was utilized. This function is employed to apply additional acceleration, angular velocity, and angular

acceleration to the momentum equation. In this study, the results for rolling motion, which is one of the six degrees of freedom (6-DOF) marine motions, were investigated. The change in body force according to the rolling angle, as well as the angular velocity and angular acceleration corresponding to the period, were input in a tabular format. The period of rotation was fixed at 10 seconds, and the analysis was conducted by classifying the maximum rotation angles into 5° , 30° , and 40° within the same period. A schematic of the rotation period and the case-specific angular velocities are presented in Figures 3 and 4.

Table III. Numerical condition for OpenFOAM transient analysis.

	Value	Remarks
Solver	buoyantPimpleFoam	
Turbulence model	RANS (SST k-omega)	
Time step	0.0005 s	Max courant number < 1
Time scheme	Euler	Implicit, First order
Target power	300 MWt	
Heat source	volumetric heat source	39X20 power distribution from Serpent
Radiation Model	N/A	
Velocity	inlet condition: 2310.75 kg/s	Non-slip condition at the wall

Figure 3. Schematic of the rotational motion over time

Figure 4. Time-dependent angular velocity for each case

2.3. Serpent calculation

The Serpent calculation was performed using the spatial temperature field obtained from the OpenFOAM analysis. The OpenFOAM temperature results were mapped onto a 39 (axial) × 20 (radial) nodal grid, and this two-dimensional temperature distribution was directly used to update the material temperatures in Serpent. Only the azimuthal variation was averaged due to the axisymmetric modeling assumption adopted to reduce computational cost.

This procedure represents a one-way coupling approach, in which the thermal-fluid results influence the neutronics calculation without thermal feedback to the CFD analysis. The purpose of this approach is not to predict reactor transient behavior under fully coupled conditions, but to evaluate the neutronic sensitivity to motion-induced spatial temperature non-uniformity in the core. The one-way coupling between OpenFOAM and Serpent is illustrated in Figure 5.

Consequently, the reactivity changes reported in this study should be interpreted as the neutronic response to spatial temperature distortion caused by ship motion, rather than as a prediction of reactivity evolution in an actual reactor system.

Figure 5. Methodology for the one-way coupling analysis between OpenFOAM and Serpent codes

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 6 illustrates the change in the core mean temperature resulting from the calculated marine motion. The 5° case exhibited a relatively weak rotational motion, leading to a mean temperature difference of less than 0.12 K, which is similar to the initial temperature behavior. However, starting from the 30° case, where the angular velocity increased, the overall mean temperature rose by approximately 2 K compared to the initial temperature of 993 K, with a maximum-to-minimum temperature difference of 2.87 K. In the 40° case, the impact of the rotational motion was further intensified, resulting in a mean temperature increase of about 3.4 K and a maximum-to-minimum temperature difference of 5.5 K. This indicates that the rotational motion leads to an increase in pressure drop due to factors such as the reduction in buoyancy and non-uniform mixing within the core, subsequently raising the overall core mean temperature.

Figure 6. Core mean temperature over time

Figure 7 presents the calculated keff values derived from the core temperature data at each time step. All values shown in the graph possess an uncertainty ranging between 12 and 15 pcm. Similar to the core mean temperature, the keff values exhibit an oscillating trend corresponding to the rotational period (10 s). Since the change in core keff is influenced by the fuel's thermal feedback, it appears as an inverse trend compared to the mean temperature behavior. Consistent with the mean temperature results, the 40° case showed the largest maximum-to-minimum keff difference, approximately 130 pcm. The difference was 119 pcm for the 30° case and 82 pcm for the 5° case. A previous study showed that the thermal feedback of the PMFR was approximately 12 pcm/K. Because the maximum mean temperature difference observed in each case did not exceed 5.5 K, the keff difference evaluated in this analysis was estimated to be larger compared to the mean temperature difference. This is assessed to be due to the rotational motion inducing localized temperature changes, with the magnitude and timing of the temperature difference caused by rotation varying depending on the position within the core.

Figure 7. Effective multiplication factor over time

To evaluate the internal temperature variation caused by the rotational motion, the time-dependent temperature was calculated at the cross-section of the central region, which corresponds to the area of the highest core power. Figure 8 displays the temperature contours for each case over time on the xy-

plane at a height of 0.975 m. In all cases, a tendency was observed where the high-temperature region and low-temperature region shifted in accordance with the rotational period. Furthermore, it was confirmed that the temperature difference increased significantly with a larger rotation angle. Notably, in the 40° case, the maximum-to-minimum temperature difference was assessed to be substantial, reaching a local difference of 100 K. Although the neutronics analysis for each time step in this study utilized the mean temperature of the core region, it is anticipated that during a transient state, this non-uniform temperature distribution and resulting temperature difference would significantly alter the shape of the power density profile, potentially leading to complex transient behaviors.

Figure 8. Temperature variation within the central core cross-section over time

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, the thermal-hydraulic behavior of the PMFR and the resulting reactivity change under marine motion were evaluated using coupled OpenFOAM and Serpent analysis. Rolling motion was assumed as the target marine motion, and three cases, categorized by maximum rotation angles of 5°, 30°, and 40°, were analyzed. The neutronics analysis was performed utilizing the temperature fields extracted at 0.5 second time intervals. The main findings of this research are as follows.

- In the thermal-hydraulic analysis, the mean temperature exhibited fluctuation in all cases corresponding to the rotational period. Furthermore, both the maximum-to-minimum temperature difference and the mean temperature increased as the rotation angle was augmented.
- In the neutronics analysis, the reactivity trend was inversely related to that of the mean temperature, and the change in reactivity was observed to be larger compared to the mean temperature difference. This is assessed to be due to the non-uniform local temperature variations occurring across different core regions.
- It was confirmed that the high-temperature region and the low-temperature region were distinctly divided by the rotational motion. This is expected to significantly influence the power density profile during an actual reactor transient state.

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